

THE ROLE OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY IN THE PERSONNEL MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

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Abstract. *The relevance of this work lies in the fact that in recent years information technologies have especially rapidly begun to enter various spheres of society. The work of the HR department was no exception. Information technologies are used at all stages: from personnel selection to payroll, accounting for pension contributions and recording the chronology of advanced training courses completed by each employee. Of course, in companies with a large staff, processing such a large volume of information would take a lot of time; in addition, it would be necessary to increase the staff of the HR department itself, which would lead to an increase in the company's operating costs. At the same time, the acquisition and use of the latest information technologies in the work of the HR department also entails a number of costs. The work contains the general structure of existing modern products for digitalization of personnel management. Also, the main factors contributing to the widespread introduction of information technologies in the field of personnel management have been identified. The main obstacles to the development of information technologies in the area under study are considered. Unfortunately, not all companies today are ready to incur the costs of the latest technologies and digitalization of a number of person management activities. At the same time, this will directly affect the company's survival in the market.*

Key words: *personnel management, personnel department, information technology, personnel, digitalization, specialist.*

РОЛЬ ИНФОРМАЦИОННЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ В СИСТЕМЕ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ ПЕРСОНАЛОМ

Аннотация. *Актуальность данной работы заключается в том, что в последние годы информационные технологии особенно быстро стали проникать в различные сферы жизни общества. Работа HR-отдела не стала исключением. Информационные технологии используются на всех этапах: от подбора персонала до расчета заработной платы, учета пенсионных отчислений и учета хронологии прохождения курсов повышения квалификации каждым сотрудником. Конечно, в компаниях с большим штатом обработка такого большого объема информации заняла бы много времени; кроме того, потребуется увеличить штат самого HR-отдела, что приведет к увеличению операционных расходов компании. В то же время приобретение и использование новейших информационных технологий в работе отдела кадров также влечет за собой ряд затрат. В работе представлена общая структура существующих современных продуктов по цифровизации управления персоналом. Также выявлены основные факторы, способствующие широкому внедрению информационных технологий в сфере управления персоналом. Рассмотрены основные препятствия на пути развития информационных технологий в исследуемой сфере. К сожалению, не все компании сегодня готовы взять на себя затраты на новейшие технологии и цифровизацию ряда видов деятельности по управлению персоналом. В то же время это напрямую повлияет на выживание компании на рынке.*

Ключевые слова: управление персоналом, отдел кадров, информационные технологии, персонал, цифровизация, специалист.

Currently, information technologies affect almost all spheres of society. This trend is associated, first of all, with the continuously growing volumes of information and tasks, the processing and solution of which manually is no longer possible. In many ways, the active development of information technology in recent years is also associated with the desire to comply with global trends in economic development.

As a result, information technology has affected such areas as personnel management.

The performance of any company is assessed through profit growth, which, in turn, is directly dependent on the quality of employee work. Personnel are the main resource for achieving the goals of any company. Every organization competes for highly qualified employees who meet the requirements for a specific vacancy, etc. In modern conditions, one employee of the HR department, thanks to the use of software, can keep records of a large number of company employees, promptly prepare a variety of reports, respond to requests, etc.

The need to introduce advanced information technologies into various spheres of society is to ensure the entry of complete information in chronological order, as well as its storage, exchange and processing. The strategic task of informatization is to maintain the competitiveness of the organization by increasing the efficiency of its activities, which, in turn, depends, among other things, on the qualifications of personnel, their further development, completion of advanced training courses, etc., ensuring effective organizational communications and increasing the productivity of individual and team work. Human resource management information systems have long been actively used in Russian companies and, in fact, have become a mandatory attribute of a modern enterprise.

Currently, in the modern economy, the use of information technology in personnel management is a prerequisite for organizing the effective activities of any company. As practice shows, with special programs in place, one HR employee can manage the affairs of hundreds of company employees. The use of computer technology makes it possible to prepare various reports on the company's personnel within a short period of time.

Thus, the urgent task is to introduce information systems and digitalization that allow improving business processes in such areas as document flow, timekeeping, personnel management, salary payment and settlement. At the same time, we note that no program today can completely replace an HR employee. It only allows you to optimize the work of the personnel officer, but does not replace him in any way [1].

Let's consider a general view of the structure of all modern personnel management products existing today: Help systems. These include legal reference systems that allow the HR manager to receive timely information about adopted changes in labor legislation, standards, including minimum requirements for employees performing certain types of work; Programs that automate certain areas of the HR service. Such programs help the HR department employee keep records of data, for example, on advanced training of employees, additional education programs, draw up reports, issue various certificates, etc.; Automated integrated personnel management systems.

Such systems allow you to automate all areas of personnel management. These include, for example, the 1C: Salary and Personnel program, which allows you to automatically keep track of the time worked by each employee, as well as calculate and pay wages, and issue various certificates. This program significantly simplifies the work of a personnel officer when calculating, for example, piecework wages, when an employee's income directly depends on a number of factors, or, for example, includes various allowances in addition to salary [2].

Information technologies, which also include a variety of databases, make it possible to simplify the recruitment of employees. Modern programs and services help, on the one hand, to help with employment, and on the other, to help the HR department employee find a suitable applicant for a vacancy. Thanks to modern digital technologies, gone are the days when applicants traveled throughout the city, and sometimes the region, in search of work. Such resources simplify the meeting between the applicant and the employer. In addition, they have the opportunity to select personnel who differ in specific characteristics, such as, for example: gender, age, level of education, place of residence, and availability of a driver's license of a certain category, readiness to move or travel. Such opportunities allow you to fill a vacant position in a short time, with a minimum of effort and time. In this case, the applicant will be required to place information about him in the program in the format of a standard resume [3].

The presence of factors hindering the development and implementation of information technologies can be combined as follows: Production. Include: lack of qualified personnel in this area or lack of special training in the program, which subsequently leads to loss of working time for independent development of programs; Economic: lack of funds from the company to purchase a new program and update it; technological: inadequacy of equipment (PC) for working with programs and services [1].

All of the above problems are internal and can be resolved at the company management level. Thus, it is possible to identify a number of prerequisites for the development of information technologies in the field of petroleum management personnel: increased competition in the labor market; constant growth in the volume of information to be processed; companies' struggle for highly qualified specialists; the desire to maximize profits and reduce company costs (thanks to new technologies in personnel management, there is no need to maintain an entire HR department in the company); the need to accumulate and systematize information about the company's personnel [2].

Problems that can be solved by introducing information technology into human resource management:

- presence of an organizational structure of territorial distribution;
- the need for systematic personnel renewal;
- the problem of selecting personnel for a vacancy with all the necessary characteristics;
- gradation of employees according to qualifications, education, work experience, which leads to difficulties in calculating wages;
- the need to organize periodic training courses, testing, etc. personnel;
- difficulties with payroll, the desire to keep accurate financial records of personnel-related expenses;

- the need to combine, centralize all knowledge and experience previously acquired by employees in a single information base and the possibility of their use by newly hired employees;
- the desire to modernize the company's work and meet current trends;
- presence of competition, including competition for highly qualified specialists;
- the need to introduce new technologies in the field of personnel selection and support.

The listed problems have a direct impact on human resource management. For his effective and maximum implementation in companies, it is necessary to introduce automated personnel management systems that optimize all processes related to personnel activities. These are the latest information technologies in the field of HRM (Human Resources Management) - human resource management systems. A modern IT system for automating personnel management ensures the consolidation of all information in a single information base, significantly simplifies the work of the HR department and makes it more efficient.

The use of modern information technologies in company personnel management gives the following positive effects: reduction of decision-making time at all levels of company management; Improving the quality of personnel decisions; Prompt preparation of reports for government agencies in accordance with legal and regulatory requirements; Reducing costs for personnel management; Increasing staff productivity; optimal use of the professional qualities of a specific company employee; personal accounting of pensions of company employees; Maintaining a complete individual work history of the company's personnel; Preparation of a management reserve and promotion of the most promising employees of the company [3].

In general terms, we can say that in modern conditions the introduction of advanced information technologies in personnel management is due to three main reasons.

Firstly, a large number of personnel, information about each of which must be accumulated, stored, supplemented and certificates prepared (if necessary). All this burden falls on the shoulders of the HR department.

Secondly, difficulties in calculating wages. In a number of companies, wages may depend on a number of factors, such as: fulfillment/non-fulfillment of the plan, availability of bonuses, actual amount of time worked, work on weekends, etc. In this case, information technologies make it possible to transfer such painstaking work as payroll calculation to automatic mode. The HR employee will only need to enter the initial data. This makes it possible to reduce the company's operating costs for maintaining a large staff of personnel accountants.

Thirdly, in knowledge-intensive sectors of the economy it is difficult to find a specialist who fully satisfies the company's requirements. In this regard, the company trains its employees itself, organizing various advanced training courses, possibly retraining, periodically conducting certification of employees and testing their current knowledge. All this work also falls on the HR department and it cannot be done without special software.

Thus, the digitalization of information technology in personnel management in a modern company takes on a leading role, since it is designed, on the one hand, to optimize the work of the HR department, reduce the company's costs, and on the other hand, to provide the company with highly qualified permanent staff, systematically increasing the level of their knowledge, supporting the company's goals and contributing to the growth of its profits.

In conclusion, we note that the introduction of information technology into the field of personnel management of a company is no longer an innovation, but, at the same time, acts as a kind of catalyst for the application and dissemination of management experience, modern management technologies that provide enterprises with and additional opportunities and competitive advantages.

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